

Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with FabLabs, Safety Experts and Customer Communities

WP3- ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development

Deliverable D3.3: "ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v2"

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

732559

ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v2

Deliverable No.	D3.3		
WP No.	3	WP title	ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development
Activity No.	T3.1- T3.4	Activity Title	Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis, ToyLabs Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component, ToyLabs Augmented Reality Component, Partner Matching and Selection Component
Authors	SLG, NTUA, AIJU		
Status	Final		
Dissemination level	Public		
File Name	TOYLABS_SLG_WP3_IR_D3.3-v1.00		
Delivery date	10 November 2017		

Version History Table

No.	Date	Author	Notes and Comments
0.1	15.05.2017	SLG	Initial ToC
0.2	21.09.2017	SLG	Exec Summary
0.3	26.09.2017	SLG	Introduction
0.4	10.10.2017	SLG	Section 2
0.5	27.10.2017	NTUA	Section 3
0.6	06.11.2017	SLG	Final draft
0.7	08.11.2017	NTUA	Internal Review
1.0	10.11.2017	SLG	Final Version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF TABLES	4
ABBREVIATIONS LIST	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1 INTRODUCTION	7
1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE	7
1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	7
1.3 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPs AND TASKS.....	7
2 UPDATED DESIGNS OF THE TOYLABS CORE PLATFORM	9
2.1 INTRODUCTION.....	9
2.2 COMPONENT’S HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE.....	10
2.3 COMPONENT’S FLOW DIAGRAMS UPDATE.....	11
2.4 MOCKUPS AND SCREENSHOTS.....	13
2.5 COMPONENTS BACKLOG UPDATE.....	19
2.5.1 <i>New User Stories</i>	19
2.5.2 <i>Omitted User Stories</i>	19
3 UPDATED DESIGNS OF THE TOYLABS MARKET AND TRENDS ANALYSIS COMPONENT	20
3.1 INTRODUCTION.....	20
3.2 COMPONENT’S HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE AND INTEGRATION TO THE TCP	20
3.3 COMPONENT’S FLOW DIAGRAMS.....	22
3.4 MOCKUPS AND SCREENSHOTS.....	24
3.5 COMPONENTS BACKLOG UPDATE.....	36
3.5.1 <i>New User Stories</i>	36
3.5.2 <i>Omitted User Stories</i>	39
4 CONCLUSIONS	41
4.1 AT A GLANCE.....	41
4.2 NEXT STEPS	41

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2-1: TCP High Level Architecture	10
Figure 2-2: User Onboarding Workflow	11
Figure 2-3: Projects Browsing Workflow	12
Figure 2-4: Product Management Workflow	12
Figure 3-1: Architecture of Market and Trend Analysis Component	21
Figure 3-2 Project Configuration Workflow	22
Figure 3-3 Trend Analysis Workflow.....	23
Figure 3-4 Social Feedback Workflow	24
Figure 3-5 ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Landing page ...	25
Figure 3-6: Project's Initialisation page.....	26
Figure 3-7: Project's Initialisation page /Advanced Settings enabled	27
Figure 3-8: Trend Analysis Set up page	28
Figure 3-9: User's Trend Analysis Saved Settings	28
Figure 3-10: Trend Analysis Custom Set up page	29
Figure 3-11 Trend Analysis Custom Set up page/ Time Settings	29
Figure 3-12 Trend Analysis Custom Set up page/ Concept Definition.....	30
Figure 3-13 Trend Analysis Custom Set up page/ Concept Definition/ Save Concept	31
Figure 3-14: Trend Analysis Dashboard	32
Figure 3-15: Social Feedback Set up page	33
Figure 3-16 Social Feedback Saved Settings.....	33
Figure 3-17 Social Feedback Custom Settings	34
Figure 3-18 Social Feedback Custom Settings/ Time Settings.....	34
Figure 3-19 Social Feedback Market Set Definition	35
Figure 3-20: Social Feedback Analysis Dashboard.....	36

LIST OF TABLES

Table I New User Stories for the Market and Trend Analysis Component..	37
Table II Updated User Stories for the Market and Trend Analysis Component	40

ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market Trend Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation

TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform
-----	-----------------------

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D3.3 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v2” is used to document the updated designs regarding the ToyLabs Core Platform and the Market Analysis Component to be implemented and integrated in the platform as tasks under WP4.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the designs, workflow diagrams and other work that has been performed under the WP3 tasks in the previous period. All these outputs, can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

D3.3 will be updated throughout the project and those amendments will result to deliverable D3.5. It will provide new insights and design document to the software development tasks of WP4, in order to gradually describe the features and functions necessary to reach a stable version of the ToyLabs MVP.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D3.3 titled as “ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v2” is used to document the updated (since D3.2) designs regarding the ToyLabs Core Platform and the Market Analysis Component which are the components that according to the agreed project implementation schedule have been prioritised during the reference period of the present deliverable.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the designs, workflow diagrams and other work that has been performed under the WP3 tasks in the previous period. All these outputs, can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D3.3 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the updates to the work started and presented in D3.2 towards defining the operations, the flows, the mockups and the elements of the backlog to be released as far as it concerns the ToyLabs Core Platform
- Section 3 refers to the ToyLabs Market and Trends Analysis Component, which is the component that has been prioritised (together with the TCP) since the delivery of D3.2, and includes all updates to the design and structure of the component.
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable, stating the next imminent steps to be executed and documented under the deliverables D3.4 & D.3.5

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

As identified in the DoA, D3.3 is tightly linked to all other WP3 deliverables, as well as to all WP4 Deliverables.

Regarding WP3, D3.3, which is a revision of D3.2, will be further revised throughout the project and will serve as the basis for deliverables D3.4 and D3.5, which all concern the updated designs and technical diagrams that will be created with a view on the upcoming releases of the ToyLabs agile development process.

With regards to WP4, D3.3 provides updates to specific design documents, which are taken into account during the development tasks. Furthermore, D3.1, D3.2 and D.3.3 act as reference documents regarding the evaluation of the output of the software development tasks, which will be constantly checked to amend as necessary the backlog and its prioritised list.

2 UPDATED DESIGNS OF THE TOYLABS CORE PLATFORM

2.1 Introduction

The Toylabs Core Platform is the main infrastructure that powers the ToyLabs platform and is the host environment for all other sub-components to be integrated.

In the previous deliverables, the main operations requested from the overall Toylabs platform which are handled by the TCP have been identified and presented. Following the development of the platform and based on the feedback received by the project partners, the main supported operations list has been expanded in order to include presentation and management of products (either completed or under development) which are characterised by their owners as public projects. Making a product public allows any visitor not involved in any way in the development of the product to get information about it and to view specific elements also defined as public (including selected designs, prototypes, 3D models, pictures etc).

In this framework, new operations have been included in the main operations list supported by TCP as follows:

- Platform Browsing
- Registration/Log In
- Profile Editing
- Organisation Selection
- Organisation Information Filling
- Organisation Management
- Participating in an Organisation
- ToyLabs Products Browsing
- Communication Actions
- Feedback Provision
- Product Initiation
- Prototype Request
- Product Handling
- Design Handling
- Prototype Handling
- AR model handling
- Feedback to Design
- Feedback to Prototype
- Feedback to AR model
- Product Information Filling
- Manufacturing Initiation
- Product Monitoring

_____ *operations already included in D3.2*

- Browsing public projects
 - View public designs
 - View public prototypes
 - Request/ Grant access to non-public elements of public projects
- _____ *additional operations introduced*

2.2 Component's High-Level Architecture

No updates have been introduced in the overall architecture of the TCP. The high-level architectural diagram of the platform, depicted in the following figure has been already described in D3.2 and is included here for reference reasons only.

Figure 2-1: TCP High Level Architecture

2.3 Component's Flow Diagrams Update

Out of the flow diagrams presented in D3.2, some changes have been introduced for optimization reasons. An additional flow diagram is provided referring to browsing public projects and providing feedback, both for final products and for active projects (products still under development).

Onboarding Process (updated)

The user is able to browse the informational pages of the ToyLabs platform which require no authorization, without being able to further interact or view toys included in the platform without logging in. In order to do so, upon landing to the user login/registration page, he is able to either log in using his credentials (in case he has been already registered in ToyLabs), or to initiate the registration process. The option to login using Google Login/ Facebook Login/ Twitter Login services has been included for making the registration and the login processes faster. For getting registered the user shall provide some information, and once he is accepted as a registered user he may choose whether to join an existing organization or create a new one. As a next step, the user is able to browse the platform's private spaces, and also to edit his profile.

Figure 2-2: User Onboarding Workflow

Public Project Browsing Process (introduced)

After logging in the platform, the user is able to browse all projects which are characterised as public. These may include already completed projects, led to the release of new toys, or active projects referring to products under development with the support of the ToyLabs platform. For such projects, the user is able to view specific elements like designs defined as public, as well as related prototypes, pictures etc. In case the user wishes to get access to non-public elements of the project, he sends a request to the product owner, who may add the user to the collaborators of the project in order to grant to him access to all related material, expecting for feedback. Either based on the public elements only (if no access is requested/granted) or on the public & the private elements of a project, the user is

able to rate the product and to provide specific feedback to the product owner to be taken into account respectively.

Figure 2-3: Projects Browsing Workflow

Product Management Process (updated)

The creation of a product on the ToyLabs platform is initiated by a user by specifying some basic information about the product. Afterwards the user is able to create different design or prototype version, and in each one add collaborators and work with them in order to improve the product. It needs to be noted, that during the whole process, specific parts (like "Add Collaborator") are supported by other components such as the PMN component. What has been introduced in this update is the creation of prototypes based on finalized designs. While the user has the option to create a prototype independently, the standard process refers to selecting one or more finalized designs and to proceed in creating prototypes based on those designs and linked to them.

Figure 2-4: Product Management Workflow

2.4 Mockups and ScreenShots

As the development of the platform has progressed, indicative screenshots are provided presenting the different screens of the TCP through which the operations are implemented.

Initial Screen and Public Elements Showcase

Products/ Designs/ Prototypes Showcase

The showcase consists of six cards arranged in two rows of three. Each card has a header with the 'TOY LABS' logo (a flask with a gear) and a category label in a colored box: 'Prototype' (orange), 'Product' (blue), or 'Design' (yellow). The cards contain Latin placeholder text and interaction metrics.

Category	Title	Description	Comments	Likes
Prototype	Ipsa aliquam quidem est.	Quia hic debitis atque officia mollitia optio et. Ut natus ut fuga eum velit. Veritatis aut ea et eaque ut maiores ullam. Et ratione quos enim rerum sapiente quos. Illum voluptatem vel quis eum....	0	0
Product	Dicta cum quo consequuntur.	Sapiente eos consequuntur quo et molestias. Perferendis voluptatum non amet sint ut enim autem. Veritatis rerum doloribus rem error occaecati et quae. Eos accusantium eveniet culpa at nulla. Enim...	17	0
Product	Dignissimos et odit expedita harum.	Et voluptatem exercitationem recusandae vero quae ipsa ut. Autem eaque vitae aut. Qui assumenda aperiam minus maxime unde. Qui minus quasi corrupti reiciendis ex natus sed. Blanditiis sit facilis...	0	0
Product	Odio omnis nesciunt voluptas qui.	Sit non officia sapiente saepe labore est qui. Unde sequi ducimus nihil rerum culpa quaerat. Dolorum facilis a voluptates qui. Facere facere expedita est consequuntur quia vitae totam. Aut quis...	0	0
Design	Design A	A short description to a public product!	0	0
Design	Quam pariatur praesentium.	Itaque et consequuntur pariatur et. Cum hic harum ut deleniti doloribus impedit expedita ullam. Nemo minus quia a unde voluptatibus voluptates. Dolores corporis vel hic. Est laudantium odio sed...	0	0

User Login via Password or via Google / Facebook

The login form is centered on the page. At the top is the 'TOY LABS' logo. Below it is a white box containing the login fields and options.

Email:

Password:

OR

Facebook:

Google:

Forgot password?

New user? Register now!

Basic Registration

[Forgot password?](#)

OR

New user? [Register now!](#)

User Profile Complete/Edit

[Products](#) [About](#) Marios Finik ▾

Edit Profile

Personal

Name

Marios Finik

Address

Address

Country

Greece

Telephone

Telephone

Facebook

http://

Twitter

http://

LinkedIn

http://

Professional

Toy Manufacturer

Organization:

Singular Logic

Owner

Cancel

Update

Create/ Edit Organisation Main Profile

Products About ✉ 🔔 2 👤 Marios Finik

Edit Organization Profile

General Facilities Services & Pricing Certifications & Awards

Name Singular Logic **Legal Name** Singular Logic LTD **Legal Form** Limited Company (LTD)

Description

Address

Street Name and Number

Postal Code Postal Code **City** Athens **Country** Greece

P.O. Box P.O. Box **Phone** Phone **Fax Number** Fax Number

Website URL http://... **Instagram** https://www.instagram.com/...

Facebook Page https://www.facebook.com/... **Twitter Account** https://www.twitter.com/...

Cancel Update

Services Information

Products About ✉ 🔔 2 👤 Marios Finik

Edit Organization Profile

General Facilities **Services & Pricing** Certifications & Awards

Services

Geographical Market(s)

Competencies

<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Toy Categories

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activity Toys	<input type="checkbox"/> Aquatic Toys	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts, Crafts Materials And Related Articles
<input type="checkbox"/> Audio/Visual Equipment	<input type="checkbox"/> Books with Play Value	<input type="checkbox"/> Colls and Soft-filled Toys
<input type="checkbox"/> Construction Toys and Puzzles	<input type="checkbox"/> Costumes, Disguises and Masks	<input type="checkbox"/> Experimental Sets
<input type="checkbox"/> Functional Toys	<input type="checkbox"/> Game Sets	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical and/or Electrical Driven Vehicles
<input type="checkbox"/> Play Scenes and Constructed Models	<input type="checkbox"/> Projectile Toys with Launching Device	<input type="checkbox"/> Push-along Toys and Walking Aids
<input type="checkbox"/> Role-playing Toys	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand-Water Toys	<input type="checkbox"/> Skill Development Toys
<input type="checkbox"/> Toy Cosmetics	<input type="checkbox"/> Toy Musical Instruments	<input type="checkbox"/> Toy Sports Equipment and Balls
<input type="checkbox"/> Toys for Babies to Look at, Grasping and/or Squeezing	<input type="checkbox"/> Toys Intended to be Entered by a Child	<input type="checkbox"/> Toys Intended to Bear the Mass of a Child

Production Scale: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

Pricing

Ways of Payment: Bank Transfer Bitcoin Check Credit Card Paypal

Paid in (delay): On Delivery 15 Days 30 Days 45 Days 60 Days 90 Days

Cancel Update

New Product Creation

New Product

[← Back to Dashboard](#)

General

Title

Description

Category **Suitable for Ages From** **To**

Legal

Who will be the legal owner of this product? Myself My Organization (Singular Logic)

! Do you want to make your product public (can be seen by everyone)? No Yes

Images

Drop files here to upload

[Create](#)

Product Designs Board & Options

Product Designs

[← Back to Dashboard](#)

Title	Version	Last Modified	Actions
Design A	1	04.10.2017	
Aspernatur velit dolore	1	04.10.2017	
Id recusandae molestiae.	1	06.07.2017	
Voluptatem enim laborum.	1	06.07.2017	

[+ Add Design](#)

ified **Edit Design**

17	
17	
17	
17	

 Add Design

id **Create new version**

7	
7	
7	
7	

 Add Design

Action **Discussions**

 Add Design

Actions **Partner Matching**

 Add Design

Actions **Create Prototype**

 Add Design

Product Prototypes Board

Product Prototypes

[← Back to Dashboard](#)

Title	Last Modified	Actions
Prototype based on Design A	05.10.2017	
Aspernatur velit dolore	05.10.2017	
Praesentium ex sit ut.	06.07.2017	

 Add Prototype

2.5 Components Backlog Update

2.5.1 New User Stories

The components backlog has been slightly updated by introducing three more user stories, related to the additional operations described in Section 2.1. However, it must be noted that the new user stories are not considered of high priority, so they are to be included in future versions of the platform.

VI.18	Platform Browsing		Visitor		to be able to provide feedback to completed projects/ products	I can send my feedback on an already released product to its owner
OU.32	Product Access Request		Ordinary User		to be able to request access to the designs, prototypes and other non-public elements of a product	I can ask for access to designs and technical material
PO.16	Product Monitoring				to be able to provide read-only access to project elements in order to get feedback	I can authorise users to access and provide feedback on non-public elements

2.5.2 Omitted User Stories

Since the previous update, one user story has been omitted, referring to the visibility of a user in the platform for transparency reasons, based on the feedback received by the project partners.

OU.4	Profile Editing		Ordinary User		to be able to make my profile "private"	I am no longer listed in the public users of the platform
------	-----------------	--	---------------	--	---	---

3 UPDATED DESIGNS OF THE TOYLABS MARKET AND TRENDS ANALYSIS COMPONENT

3.1 Introduction

This component is intended to give the user an easy-to-use tool that will provide him with the appropriate information - through various, intuitive charts- to help him on the one hand identify market trends for his domain of interest and on the other hand gain a deeper understanding of customers' satisfaction and dissatisfaction on specific topics (either products/toys or brands) and as a result on their brand perception, campaign efficiency and competitors' position in the market.

Through this component, the toy manufacturer, or any intended user, will be able to:

- Explore visual analytics and gain insights on how trends are being generated in web and social media;
- Interact with the analytics and draw useful conclusions on emerging market trends for the toy industry that may serve, combined with the manufacturer's experience, as recommendations and initial, raw ideas about future toy designs;
- Acquire social feedback on specified by the manufacturer terms of interest;
- Gain deeper and quantitative insights on crowd's perception about a brand or brand's product;
- Explore comparative visual graphs about a manufacturer's market position (as reflected by both the number and semantics of mentions in web) in comparison with their competitors' position.

3.2 Component's High-level Architecture and Integration to the TCP

The Market and Trend Analysis component consists of three main, distinct parts; the User Interface, the Communication Layer and the Natural Language Processing and Analytics engine. Figure 3-1 depicts the component's high level architecture, namely these three layers along with their internal structure.

The **User Interface** is responsible for providing the user with insights into the collected data, while guiding him to apply filters, make intuitive queries and browse the results through advanced visualisations. The component's User Interface in question is integrated in the core platform's User Interface. The basic technologies used for this layer are PHP and JavaScript.

The **Communication layer** manages and directs the flow of data between the two other layers, namely the component's User Interface and the Analytics engine. The Python Django REST framework will be used for this purpose, in conjunction with a TCP module that will handle the authorisation and the communication between the UI and the Python portion of the analytics engine.

Finally, the **Natural language processing and analytics engine** is responsible for the data retrieval, data processing and the implementation of all required computations to perform emotion analysis and identify trending topics. As a result, this layer is used to extract data from source and process them in a way that can feed the web interface. The basic technologies that are used are the “Elasticsearch” engine, the “Couchbase server” database, the “NLTK” framework and the “Scikit learn” library.

The Market and Trend Analysis component gets integrated in the ToyLabs Core Platform by expanding the platform’s user interface and connecting the engine to the backend. As seen in Figure 3-1, the integration takes place in the platform’s middle application logic layer through a list of API calls that will request specific information from the module. The module’s frontend is being integrated, as already stated, using JavaScript and the libraries D3 and AMCHARTS. It is based on the built-in modules of VueJS to communicate with a RESTful API. The module stores its data in a separate database than that of the core platform. Finally, the user initialises the module in the product development’s Research phase, which is the second phase after concept definition, and prompts the user to start either a Market Trends or a Social Feedback analysis.

Figure 3-1: Architecture of Market and Trend Analysis Component

3.3 Component's Flow Diagrams

In this section, all updates in the component's flow diagrams, with respect to the ones presented in the context of D3.2, are presented.

All updates were made in the light of the better and easier understanding of the workflow and way of use of the component by its users. Therefore, a simplification of the procedure was attempted.

In this context, the first workflow presented in Figure 3-2 has to do with the configuration of each newly created project. The user must initialise a harvester in order to start a trend or a social feedback analysis and this is achieved via a group of user settings on the platform. These settings are related to the data sources that are to be used for the analysis, the keywords, hashtags or phrases considered to be relevant to the analysis that will follow, and which must be included in the harvesting data and data's language.

The data's allowable publication times are being removed as a filtering option from the "Project Configuration Workflow" since harvesting will take place from the starting date of the project until the current date. This filtering will only be considered for the two consecutive workflows for Trend Analysis and Social Feedback, as will be described along the following lines.

Furthermore, the option to create market sets during the project configuration process is also removed, and remains as an option only for the Social Feedback Analysis.

Figure 3-2 Project Configuration Workflow

After the configuration of the project and when the user receives a notification email that data harvesting has been completed successfully, he may choose to either start a Trend or a Social Feedback analysis process.

Starting with the Trend Analysis workflow, according to the flow diagram that is presented in Figure 3-3, the user may either load past saved search settings or configure the search settings for his analysis, starting from the harvester (i.e. project configuration) ones. In that view, he may restrict search parameters on specific keywords, sources, languages or influencers' accounts for the analysis that will follow. He may afterwards provide to the platform additional settings regarding the time period for the analysis, being able to go back in time and compare analysis reports. Finally, before starting the analysis, the user is requested to provide specific meaningful concepts of interest (i.e. baby dolls) and parameters (e.g. colour, material) that will be presented and formulate the visualisations accordingly in order to provide to the user useful and meaningful information customized to his needs and industry's "language". After that, he can initiate a trend analysis and apply specific filters to charts in order to acquire the needed information. The user can also save these preferences for future use.

Figure 3-3 Trend Analysis Workflow

Finally, Figure 3-4 represents the flow diagram for the user that wants to implement Social Feedback analysis. For the social feedback analysis, the user is firstly asked to either load a past saved search for social feedback or to configure the search settings for his analysis, starting from the harvester settings. This, as well as the two consecutive steps, come in direct alignment with the Trend Analysis Workflow, since here also the user is requested to optionally configure further certain search parameters and specify the time period of the analysis.

After that, the user is asked either to create a new market set for the social feedback analysis or to choose one from his saved market sets. The "market set" as introduced and defined in the context of ToyLabs is a representation of the market for the manufacturer in question as he perceives it. Therefore, the manufacturer is asked to provide how the Market and Trend Analysis component will search for his brand (i.e. keywords), his products, as well as for his competitors

and competitors' products. Each market set may be a subset of the market as the manufacturer want to represent it for his analysis. To make it clearer, not necessarily all his competitors or all his products are listed in each market set, but only the ones that he wants to compare for the specific analysis needs.

Afterwards, the manufacturer may choose either a “simple” analysis for his brand and products or a comparative one, taking into account also the competitors' presence.

Then the user can start social feedback analysis and apply, as was the case in trend analysis, specific filters to charts in order to take the information he needs and to save these preferences for future use.

Figure 3-4 Social Feedback Workflow

It needs to be highlighted that this alignment between Trend Analysis Workflow and Social Feedback Workflow, that drove the changes from the workflows presented in D3.2, aims to simplify the steps for the user and provide an easier-to-use component.

3.4 Mockups and ScreenShots

In this section, the updated Mock-ups, to serve the workflows described above, are presented. It needs to be mentioned that orange “notes” are being used inside certain mock-ups to explain issues that may not be completely straightforward visually and may need further explanation.

Figure 3-5 ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Landing page

ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Initialisation

← → ↻

Initialise Project

Provide a name for your project

Included Keywords or hashtags

key1 OR key2 OR key3

key1, key2,... etc. may represent a word, a phrase or a hashtag

[+ Advanced Settings](#)

Sources

Source type:

Facebook
 Twitter
 Blogs

Specify Source:

Request new blog pages

Language:

Influencers

Define Influencers' s Accounts

<https://twitter.com/Baulchtweet>
https://twitter.com/richa_dikshit
<https://twitter.com/PGuinaudeau>

Figure 3-6: Project's Initialisation page

ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Initialisation

← → ↻

Initialise Project

Provide a name for your project

Included Keywords or hashtags

key1 OR key2 OR key3

[- Advanced Settings](#)

key1 AND key2 AND key3...

OR

key1 AND key2 AND key3...

"+" button indicates the possibility to add an extra "key1 AND key2..." structure separated by an OR

A NOT(key) (i.e. exclude such keywords/hashtags/key phrases) is also considered, although not depicted

Sources

Source type:

Facebook

Twitter

Blogs

Specify Source:

https://vk.com/my_dolls_ru

www.toyblog.com

Request new blog pages

Language:

Influencers

Define Influencers' s Accounts

<https://twitter.com/Baulchtweet>

https://twitter.com/richa_dikshit

<https://twitter.com/PGuinaudeau>

Figure 3-7: Project's Initialisation page /Advanced Settings enabled

Figure 3-8: Trend Analysis Set up page

Figure 3-9: User's Trend Analysis Saved Settings

ToyLabs Trend Analysis Custom Settings

← → ↻

Settings for trend analysis

Custom Settings | Time Settings | Concept's Definition

Confine & Customise your trend analysis settings

Included Keywords or hashtags

[- Advanced Settings](#)

key1 AND key2 AND key3.

OR

key1 AND key2 AND key3.

Source type: **Language:** ▾

Influencers:

Figure 3-10: Trend Analysis Custom Set up page

ToyLabs Trend Analysis Time Settings

← → ↻

Settings for trend analysis

Custom Settings | Time Settings | Concept's Definition

Time: From ▾ To ▾

or

Live Last 7 days
 Last month
 Last year

Figure 3-11 Trend Analysis Custom Set up page/ Time Settings

ToyLabs Trend Analysis Concept Definition

← → ↻

☰

Settings for trend analysis

Custom Settings
Time Settings
Concept's Definition

Concept Definition

*Concept is a **meaningful** representation of your organisation's interests that can be defined through a **combination of keywords, phrases & hashtags**.
The trend analysis that follows will demonstrate analytics and comparison among the chosen concepts*

New concept

OR

Baby doll concept

Do you want to add any existing concepts for your analysis?

Define parameters for the analysis

Default Parameters

Colours Include

Materials Include

Define your own parameter

Input a name

Type existing concepts' names ▼

- Item One
- Monster doll
- Custom dolls

One parameter could be "Categories"
(e.g. matryoshka, porcelain, reborn, china, hopi, kachina, paper, action figure, puppet, etc.)

Figure 3-12 Trend Analysis Custom Set up page/ Concept Definition

ToyLabs Trend Analysis Concept Definition

← → ↻

Settings for trend analysis

Concept Definition

*Concept is a **meaningful** representation of your organisation's interests that can be defined through a **combination of keywords, phrases & hashtags**.
The trend analysis that follows will demonstrate analytics and comparison among the chosen concepts*

New concept

OR

Successfully saved!

Do you want to add more new concepts?

Do you want to add any existing concepts for your analysis?

Define parameters for the analysis

Default Parameters

Colours Include

Materials Include

Define your own parameter

Input a name

Type existing concepts' names ▼

- Item One
- Monster doll
- Custom dolls

Figure 3-13 Trend Analysis Custom Set up page/ Concept Definition/ Save Concept

Figure 3-14: Trend Analysis Dashboard

Figure 3-15: Social Feedback Set up page

Figure 3-16 Social Feedback Saved Settings

ToyLabs Social Feedback Custom Settings

← → ↻

Settings for Social Feedback

Custom Settings | Time Settings | Market Set Definition

Confine & Customise your trend analysis settings

Included Keywords or hashtags

[- Advanced Settings](#)

key1 AND key2 AND key3.

OR

key1 AND key2 AND key3.

Source type: **Language:** ▼

Influencers:

Figure 3-17 Social Feedback Custom Settings

ToyLabs Social Feedback Time Settings

← → ↻

Settings for Social Feedback

Custom Settings | Time Settings | Market Set Definition

Time: From ▼ To ▼

or

Live Last 7 days
 Last month
 Last year

Figure 3-18 Social Feedback Custom Settings/ Time Settings

ToyLabs Social Feedback Market Set Definition

← → ↻

Settings for Social Feedback

Market Set

Define how to search for your brand name & products and your competitors for a comparative social feedback analysis

Choose from saved market sets

Create a new Market Set

My Brands

Brand Name

Please fill your brand name (one or more)
Juema

Competitor 1: Mattel

Competitor 2: Habro

...

Competitor 3: Lamilly

+

use "+" to add another set for comparison

My Products

Product Name

Please fill your product name (one or more)
Paola Reina

Competitive product 1: Barbie

Competitive product 2: Baby

...

Competitive product 3: Lamilly

+

Figure 3-19 Social Feedback Market Set Definition

Figure 3-20: Social Feedback Analysis Dashboard

3.5 Components Backlog Update

3.5.1 New User Stories

New User Stories are defined in the context of this deliverable in order to further specify the requirements that this component aims to satisfy.

Table I New User Stories for the Market and Trend Analysis Component

#	EPIC	As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
MA.28	M & T Analysis Setup ¹		Manufacturer		to be able to provide a name and save my different projects		I can have different projects according to my needs
MA.29	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to specify specific social media accounts of interest for data extraction		I can highlight the importance of these accounts for my industry and be sure that the analysis results take them into account
MA.30	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select the language of posts/data to retrieve		I can get analysis results from the languages of my interest
MA.31	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to be able to search for an "advanced" combination of words and wordphrases in the Market and Trends Analysis module		I can further specify and better formulate my areas of interest and get targeted insights
MA.32	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to be able to exclude words and wordphrases from my analysis		I can further specify and better formulate my areas of interest and get targeted insights
MA.33	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to be able to insert specific social media accounts perceived as influential		I can underline the importance of their opinion for the way trends are formed
MA.34	MT & SF Analysis Setup ²		Manufacturer		to explore saved settings for both my Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis		I can avoid configuring each new analysis from scratch
MA.35	MT & SF Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to customise the initial settings used for harvesting for both my Market Trend and Social Feedback Analysis		I can further restrict and specify the data space for the analysis

¹ Market & Trends Analysis Setup

² Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Setup

MA.36	MT & SF Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to specify the time interval from which the analysis (both for Market Trends and Social Feedback) will come from	I can be able to compare social media sources results for the past until now
MA.37	MT Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to specify and save meaningful concepts and words combinations	I can get visualisations, analysis results and comparisons for these specific concepts of interests
MA.38	SF Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to define how the Social Feedback module should search for my brand name & my products	I can afterwards get informed insights for the crowd's perception about my brand & products
MA.39	SF Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to be able to specify my competitors and their products	I can understand my company's position in the market as reflected in social media
MA.40	MT Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to understand the underlying sentiments for my saved concepts from the settings	I can understand if they are seen in a positive or negative way by the social media users
MA.41	MT Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see if there are any correlations among my saved concepts from settings	I can understand if any meaningful combinations may arise for a new toy design
MA.42	MT Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to explore my saved concepts according to specific parameters	I can compare the different concepts accordingly
MA.43	SF Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to be able to see the evolution of my brand's and products mentions, as well as my competitors ones, in time	I can detect any changes regarding crowd's perception in time
MA.44	SF Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to compare crowds' perception about my brand in relation with my competitors in user-friendly diagrams	I can early identify any weak or strong points of my brand in comparison with my competitors
MA.45	SF Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to get the prevailing emotions in social media about my brand, my products and my competitors	I can easily understand crowd's perception

3.5.2 Omitted User Stories

In D3.2 a first version of the user stories for the Market and Trends Analysis Component was presented that tried to remain in a high-level in order to represent a generic description of the component and avoid becoming more specific before acquiring feedback from the trials about the component and their further requirements. In that view, there are no totally omitted user stories, but only updated ones that aim to better clarify them and are presented in the following table.

Table II Updated User Stories for the Market and Trend Analysis Component

#	EPIC	As a	ROLE	I want	GOAL/DESIRE	, so that	BENEFIT
MA.19	M & T Analysis Generic		Manufacturer		I want to be able to understand crowd's perception about my brand & products		I can understand the sentiment of users on a product or a manufacturer as discussed in web2.0 channels
MA.20	M & T Analysis Generic		Manufacturer		I want to be able to explore market trends		I can get insights of trends in the toy sector, using web2.0 channels
MA.21	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select the social media channels to be used by the Market and Trends Analysis module		I can isolate or combine sources and get insights on crowd perception as expressed in specific social media sources
MA.22	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select other web sources (blogs/forums/pages) to be used by the Market and Trends Analysis module		I can get insights addressed specifically at my industry's interests
MA.23	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to select specific words and wordphrases that should be included or not in the posts/data that the Market and Trends Analysis module will retrieve		I can specify the areas of my interest and get appropriate analysis
MA.24	M & T Analysis Setup		Manufacturer		to enable the "influencers' mode" of the Market and Trends Analysis module		I can find people with influencing power in a broad web audience on a specific topic
MA.25	M & T Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see the positive, negative and other online comments on my product or my brand from the Social Feedback module		I can define a strategy for improvement
MA.26	M & T Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see visualised analytics based on the results of the Market Trends or Social Feedback module		I can better understand the results of the module
MA.27	M & T Analysis Visualisation		Manufacturer		to see related concepts about search terms		I can get a better idea about trends and users' feedback

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 At a glance

D3.3 includes the updated design documents which are provided for the development of the ToyLabs Core Platform, as well as for the Market and Trends Analysis Component, which are the components on which most effort has been put during the reference period from the delivery of D3.2 to date.

All progress and the latest updated data which formulate the core material upon which WP4 works to deliver the software platform, are available the project's GitHub account at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>.

As an update to D3.2, the present deliverable introduces some changes and additions to be considered during the development of the ToyLabs MVP.

4.2 Next Steps

As discussed in the introduction, D3.3 will be updated throughout the project and those amendments will result to deliverables D3.4 and finally D3.5. Each one of those new versions, will provide new insights and design document to the software development tasks of WP4, in order to gradually describe the features and functions necessary to reach a stable version of the ToyLabs MVP. Furthermore, additional changes to the backlog might be also introduced in those revised versions, by adding new user stories or by removing some obsolete ones, resulting into specific changes to the MVP.